

Interview transcript STE *Law and policy*

Interview date: 02.06.2023

Participants: P7

I [00:00:01] I think it's much easier than. One moment. Okay. Nice. So, yeah, regarding the time. So I plan for one and a half hours, and normally I would take around 15 minutes for an introduction around an explanation of the methodology and around 60 minutes for the real interview and 15 minutes for a feedback round. And does it work for you, or do you have any time constraints?

P7 [00:00:45] No, I think in in general, but I have a bit of a time issue that I didn't, um, I didn't. I have like two agendas and um, my other, for my other work, I have to be in Wageningen for the screening at 5:30. I have dinner there. Okay. And then I have to leave by car at the latest at four and my car is not far away, but I really need to go like.

I [00:01:14] Okay.

P7 [00:01:15] To be done a little earlier then. So an hour and a half. Yeah. It's a bit on the long side.

I [00:01:22] Okay. Yeah. I mean, we can try to keep it short.

P7 [00:01:24] If it could be a little shorter. That would be. Yeah.

I [00:01:26] So I've also done interviews with two people and then I needed one and a half hours. But I think since you're only one person, I think it's, it's feasible in less than one and a half hour.

P7 [00:01:37] Okay.

I [00:01:39] So maybe I quickly introduce myself. So I'm I [interviewer]. I'm currently studying at the University of Osnabrück in Germany and my program is called Environmental Systems and Resource Management, and I write my thesis in collaboration with the Potsdam Institute of Climate Impact Research. So that's also how I got in touch with a Decade of Action. And yeah, all of you basically. And the topic is positive social tipping for regenerative agriculture. And personally, I yeah, I've always been interested in like environmental processes and social processes. So agriculture kind of combined both for me. So it was a bit the perfect fit and I'm not sure to what extent you were involved in the Earth Day last year. So the Earth Day around positive social tipping. Did you participate or not?

P7 [00:02:34] No, I just started working for ORGANISATION since September, so I wasn't there at the first.

I [00:02:40] Okay.

P7 [00:02:40] J. was, but I wasn't. Yeah.

I [00:02:42] Okay. Yeah, maybe I quickly I mean, explain what happened. So they were like, they did different groups for different subtopics. So there were topics like law and policy, finance, land access, education, and for each group they collected intervention points, so how the transition to regenerative agriculture could happen. And so we had like the results were like maps in the end with a lot of a lot of post-its on it, kind of like, yeah, a lot of different elements, interventions, things like this. And I kind of categorised them a little bit, reduced them, and that's what we will discuss today. So I have like post-its prepared and we go into the post-its that are already existing and start with that and then we see how the interview goes. So just as a little background and yeah, but maybe, yeah, you could also quickly introduce yourself with your background and your relation to regeneration, regenerative agriculture. That would be great.

P7 [00:03:54] So I studied criminology, um, and there I did my research on climate litigation. So, and that is so against companies but also against the government, on not taking the right steps against climate change and mostly from policy perspectives. And from that on I started, I started working in different projects that were on sustainability and, and climate and education, but also like making the translation from. Do you still see me? I don't know my screen just.

I [00:04:34] I see you. Yeah.

P7 [00:04:36] Okay. And um, so a lot of different things and translating science to society, I think that sort of science communication. So that's my work. I also worked as a freelancer and in the last few years I started to get more attention to like the food system and food transition because I think that's high. Yeah. It's such a. Yeah. Everything comes together with these themes. And so I started working also on a project alone using human faeces in an agriculture. It's one of the biggest leaks, so to say, in the system in a full cycle. And we don't know. Most people don't know about this. They think it's dirty and and embarrassing, but actually it's really nutritious and and good. As long as you composted and ferment it in the right way, like what you do with cows or it it's a waste of food. Um, and it's actually highly effective. Really good. And more science is being built along this topic, but it's still being seen as something like a last resort. And that's something that is vital and part of the system. So I work, I made a documentary along tis with another, for the last two years, and that's, um, and I think that's going really well. That's nice. Do a lot of project with artist and design in this

topic. And, and I met PERSONAL INFORMATION. So now I have project mostly also along the line of more the science part and campaign building campaigns. But one of the most important topics of pesticides and getting rid of pesticide use in farming. Really interesting aso. So that's me.

I [00:06:36] Nice. Yeah. Perfect. Thank you. Um, so, yeah, I mean, already wrote this. But yeah, we today we were focus on law and policy. I hope that's okay for you.

P7 [00:06:48] Yeah. Of course.

I [00:06:49] And for me this. So I call it social tipping element, but it's kind of a subsystem. So for me, the subsystem encompasses maybe two parts. One is really the governmental level of governmental support for, yeah, regenerative, sustainable agriculture. And the second one is what kind of support the government can provide. And the goal is really to find out how exactly the interventions that were named regarding law and policy, um, mainly last year and the workshops contribute to the transition to regenerative agriculture and for regenerative agriculture, I will quickly post the definition into the chat. I did it for each interview, um, and I would prefer not to discuss it too much because I know there's a lot of debate on around, okay, how do we define regenerative agriculture? Just if you agree, it's good. But if you have huge objections, of course we can. You can say it and we can quickly discuss it. Um, yeah.

P7 [00:08:06] Yeah, I know him. Yeah. Okay. No, no, I have nothing against this.

I [00:08:12] Perfect yeah, right. It's like from Wageningen the definition, I think right. Yeah. Yeah. So the output of this interview will be, again, a map or a mind map, something like this. And I will use this mind map to analyse the effects of different interventions. And I will also try to combine some maps of different subsystems. So for example, law and policy with education or with information feedbacks and so on. So that's the idea. So quickly, I will quickly share my screen. Um. So it might. So you might need to make it a little bit bigger. You can put it on full screen. You can't see anymore then, but it's not too important.

P7 [00:09:05] How do you do it?

I [00:09:06] There is like on the right upper corner of this presentation, there is like a full screen button.

P7 [00:09:17] Yeah, now I can see things.

I [00:09:18] Nice. Okay. Um, so I quickly explain the interview set up and. Oh. So I categorised the elements from last year into three categories, like three categories. So the first is intervention. So this is really the collection of elements that came from the workshops last year. And then there are conditions, and conditions are elements that I extracted also from the workshops, but also from literature. And they are really seen as elements that enable the transition process to happen. So they need to be fulfilled. So that transition to regenerative agriculture can, can happen. And yeah to make the difference a bit more clear. So a condition, for example, is farmers access to financial resources. So this is really something that need to be there. Otherwise it's not possible. And intervention on the other side is providing a transition funding. So it's more a concrete measure which can lead to the intervention in the end, to the condition. A consequence is more like a free space for elements that results from the conditions. So what happens if farmers have access to financial resources? That can be a consequences or result, consequences more negative? But it's also rather meant positive in a way. And for the interview, we go through this three categories step by step, but also look at all of them together. And for me, it would be really good if we could also focus on the interconnection between the elements. So the interconnections within one of these categories, so for example, the interconnections between the elements within interventions, but also the interconnections between these three categories and, and for the interconnections, there is a specific guideline. So there are two kinds of different influences. So there are positive interconnections and negative interconnections. And positive interconnection means that the two variables change in the same direction. And so if A decrease, increase, B increase, and if A decrease, B also decrease. And a negative interconnection means that the two variables change in opposite direction. So if A increase B decrease, if A decrease B increase. And four example, yeah, if the demand for regenerative agriculture increases, there's also a bigger market for regenerative products. So that's would be a positive relation and yes. So do you have any questions regarding this?

P7 [00:12:16] No, not for the moment if they come up during the interview.

I [00:12:18] Yeah. No worries.

P7 [00:12:20] And so maybe I'm going to put in my my ear so. Sorry.

I [00:12:25] Yeah.

P7 [00:12:56] No weird. It's connecting to my phone, but my phone is all the way downstairs, so.

I [00:13:02] Oh, okay.

P7 [00:13:05] So I'll leave it then. Yes.

I [00:13:09] Um.

P7 [00:13:10] Yes.

I [00:13:10] So, yeah, I think I would give you now, maybe, or you just let me know when you're done, that you read through the post-its that are already there, just to get familiar with them.

P7 [00:13:24] What's that? Sorry.

I [00:13:26] So I will give you now, like, a few minutes to read through the post-its that are already there to, to get familiar with them. Just let me know when you're done.

P7 [00:13:37] Yeah.

I [00:13:38] Can you read all of them?

P7 [00:13:43] I can read all of them. Mm. Yes. Yeah, I read all of them.

I [00:14:13] Okay. Perfect. So I would like to start with the conditions so simply the post-its in the middle. And yeah, again, it's really about what is needed so that the transition process can happen with regard to the law and policy system. And from the other interviews, I had the feeling that general governmental support was super important. So I put this level of governmental support also as a condition. But at the same time, the question for me is where is the governmental support important? So why does, why do we need and, for what conditions do we need the governmental support? And so this would be my first question. What do you think is the most important thing where we need governmental support, rather, from the post-its that are already there? But if you can think of something else, you can also we can also add post-its and. Yeah.

P7 [00:15:11] Yeah. Well, I think one of the conditions that is really highly important, which is not on the formal level with an informal level, is the trust in the government. Mm hmm. And I think that's on every level. The basis of that policy is actually effective. This is also the connection to the community in that sense and knowing what they need and also having a much better picture of the reality that the farmers are working in, which I think is not currently happening. So there's a big gap between, on the one hand, understanding what farmers need, how they're working, um, their lived experiences and also, um, it's not combined with, yeah, it's not a realistic policy sometimes I think that is needed. So, so on the one hand it's like, you know, like I said, the trust in the system, but it has a lot of impact if the system, the government itself don't really listen, don't really know what's going on, don't really

know, what is actually policy that is needed. And then what happens, I think in a lot of the cases is translated into policy that seems effective. That seems to be on, for example, carbon reduction very specifically. For example, there's a farmer I know that was explaining that in their dairy farm they need to put the water level up, um, for carbon reduction. So it's a very specific policy saying, okay, you, you as farmers need to do this because this is happening. But then they don't really look at the farm specific areas. So with regenerative agriculture, it's very important to have the context.

I [00:17:05] Um. Mm hmm.

[00:17:07] That you on the context of the farms that they're farming. And then she said it's like taking the water level up has a lot of impact on my farm, and we're doing it, but it has a lot of negative impact, that are not really measured through this direct policy. And they're not looking at all the different other interactions that are also connected to the specific. So I think that's a really important condition that that's it's yeah, again, it's not so simple that okay, we take this next and then it's that's the solution. You have to take the solution to the whole system itself, the land that is there and that's very context based.

I [00:17:54] Um.

P7 [00:17:56] That's something I'm thinking of now.

I [00:18:01] That it's just right. So you say that for the transition to happen, we need like regulations or we need policies, but these policies need to be context specific, and for that we need a government that is connected to the farmers and the community.

P7 [00:18:20] Yes.

I [00:18:20] Okay.

P7 [00:18:21] Yeah. Also and also more understanding of what is actually done. So you have the definition here and I think there's a lot of discussion in one hand on what the definition is.

I [00:18:33] Mm hmm.

P7 [00:18:34] Um, but there's also, I think, a lot of already clarity on what to be and what the definition should be. And I think that communicating that to policymakers, I don't know if that's a condition. Maybe that's a consequence. I'm not sure, but it's not. The clarity on this level needs to be more there.

I [00:18:55] Okay.

P7 [00:18:56] Policymakers should should be better informed also, so it's on an informal, on an information basis. But it's also on the other level. It's on if they don't have the information, then they don't translate it to the policy, then you don't get trust. But if there's more trust and you really look at the whole community itself, but also you have the information to get the right policy in check, I think it's like an interaction in that sense.

I [00:19:26] Mm hmm. Mm. I will quickly write it down.

P7 [00:19:32] Mm hmm.

I [00:19:35] Okay, so you said that, um, the information about regenerative agriculture, a clear definition is needed for the government to to take actions? Um, is that's what you?

P7 [00:19:50] Yeah.

I [00:19:51] Okay.

P7 [00:19:52] Yeah, I think in a lot of ways, for example, you have, um, one of the things that I see happening that you have, for example, nature based agriculture right now, but that's one of the many definitions that is being used. Um, and a lot of policymakers are confusing all the different definitions also because there are so many, but also because they don't really understand the level of what regenerative agriculture actually is. And it can help in so many circumstances, like you said, on a socio economic or um, on a natural, it's like biodiversity, like on every level it can help in different ways. So I think if, if policymakers understand better what regenerative agriculture actually is more than just a pilot, it's more, you know, there's a lot of piloting going on in policy. Oh we experiment a little bit with this and farmers can use this and if they get subsidies for this, you know, that's very, very much um, it's not connected. But regenerative agriculture is really look at the complete picture of the situation of the farmer, of the land, of the people. It's more than just a pilot. It's more than just one. Uh, okay, one policy and check, and then everything else happens. It's, it's much more complete transition, you know, of the system. And I think if policymakers understand better of, um, what the consequences in a positive way are or regenerative agriculture. They can make better policy that actually is not so specific on one thing and one goal.

I [00:21:35] Mm hmm.

P7 [00:21:36] Um, and more on the holistic perspective.

I [00:21:41] Yeah. I will add something like policymakers need holistic understanding. Something like this.

P7 [00:21:46] Yeah, yeah, nice.

I [00:21:48] Okay. Um, could you again say, how would you connect the trust to the government, to the other post-its?

P7 [00:21:56] Um, I think with the, you know, the farmer protest in the Netherlands of course. Mm hmm. Have you heard about the protesting?

I [00:22:03] Yeah, I've just heard that there is a lot of discussions going on at the moment in Netherlands regarding policy and stuff like this. Yeah, yeah.

P7 [00:22:11] Yeah. Um, I think, um, again, a lot of the, the distrust is about also not having the, the best regulation or the best policies in check so that the consequences are that the farmers need to be bought out because they have too much nitrogen disposition, uh, and therefore, um, and risk for the natural environment and then they need to be bought out of being a farmer. Actually that is the consequence because they, they don't know what to do in the long run. They don't know how to look at the whole picture and then they're just buying out farmers, which is their identity and actually their, their livelihoods for it to. They think that is that it is good and it seems like a solution, but it's actually making it worse and worse. And uh, and also then I don't think that in that sense farmers trust that governments understand them and understand them, their identity as a farmer, but they also don't understand farming in itself and what is needed. So I think again, it's a combination of not knowing what to do. And of course it's pretty complicated, but also not, uh, taking into account that extreme feeling of identity that farmers have. I think I think worldwide you can almost say it's an universal thing it's more than a job, it's more than, uh, what they do, it's what they are. Um, so I think that the distrust also comes from that people don't understand where they're coming from and how hard they work and how they have been trust, trusting that people say, No, you have to use artificial fertiliser, use pesticides. It's good, it's good for the land. You get more, more money or more, um, yields. Um, and they get all this misinformation as well. So I think, um, and now they have to do the opposite of all that all of a sudden. So there's also a lot of distrust coming from that history.

I [00:24:24] I See. Okay. And then try to connect it somehow. Um, so what would happen if there would be trusts or farmers would implement or would more be willing to?

P7 [00:24:47] Well, at least there will be certainly less resistance.

I [00:24:50] Mm hmm. Mm hmm.

P7 [00:24:53] Uh, and more understanding of what is needed. I think there's a lot of kind of anger coming from a lot of farmers. I think that's a big obstacle at the moment of people actually going forward, for example, we have the the discussions on the, um. Yeah, it's like a government [?]. I don't know how you say, on farming in the Netherlands has been going on for months and months, and, um, they're not coming further also because of this distrust, I think, and also because they're, they don't want to make people more angry, becoming more careful, and they're afraid to taking the the wrong steps and making the right, the wrong policy. And it ends up being one of the biggest hurdles, I think, in going forward to actually getting the transition there that we need in helping and supporting the farmers that they need to go forward. Um, so.

I [00:25:57] Okay. Maybe like this.

P7 [00:26:02] Farmers attitude, but also to the policy makers because the farmers don't trust the government. Also, the policymakers are becoming more careful in setting policy in place because they want to get farmers more angry. So in that sense, it also interacts in a way.

I [00:26:23] So policymakers. I'll write the same.

P7 [00:26:29] Yeah, yeah. Makers are hesitant, are more hesitant.

I [00:26:40] Are more hesitant. That's right. Okay. And this would lead to less regular, less strict regulations in the end.

P7 [00:26:51] Strict regulation. Yeah. We have to make some hard decisions? There are some farmers that are gonna lose in this transition because they're not able to transition anymore. And I think there's also a lot of winners, but there are even more losers now because decisions are not being made.

[00:27:10] Mm hmm.

[00:27:11] Yes. It's so high intense and it enables such, so much again, resistance that we're not going forward. So I think.

I [00:27:24] Okay.

P7 [00:27:25] In a social point of view, I think that is one of the biggest obstacles actually in policy itself is that they don't want to take the wrong steps as they did before and then they don't take any steps.

I [00:27:37] Okay. I see. Yeah. Yeah. And. Okay. Yeah. Nice. Actually, super interesting. I didn't think about that, actually so far, so perfect. And so I will leave that like it is. And so I have, like, a collection of other elements that were mentioned in the workshop last year. What do you think about them? Are they important in this sense? Are could we rather neglect them.

P7 [00:28:14] Like the one below?

I [00:28:16] Yeah. So these ones.

P7 [00:28:19] The market? Yeah. Yeah. They're. They're really important, I think. Um, but in the sense that how do I explain. Why I'm saying these things about trust and about the social capacity and how it's actually causing it to be taking longer or not actually being effective is because I think the base layer is, is that interaction because all the law and policy seems and all the different angles that you can go with financial support or. They're really important, but they're not going anywhere if that sort of base layer is not in check. They will not be effective at all. So I think the first is about building those relationship and understanding, understanding what is needed, having those conversations. And I think for it to be faster, there needs to be regulation on this level because we're actually not going anywhere. We need actually to take steps ahead because otherwise, like for example, we have the carbon credits at the moment. I'm not really a big fan of the carbon credits for farmers, but it's one of the the lesser tools that are there to give financial support to farmers to actually go forward. So in a sense there's a lot of, yeah, policies that need to be in check, but they will not be the on the long run. The systemic change will not coming from that, you know. Um, but of course, they are really important.

I [00:29:58] Yeah, I see.

P7 [00:29:59] Yeah. And we need to start from somewhere, you know? So I think.

I [00:30:03] Yeah, but I. I completely see what you mean. So I mean, to have these aspects and to get to this market access, access to land and so on, we kind of need the regulations from the governance so we need this whole process that you describe before because otherwise the government would not or will not like do anything. Right. So that's.

P7 [00:30:28] Yeah, Yeah. And there's also in a sense that, what I see happening is that you have on a formal level policy that is needed, that is. It needs to be put in place and it's taking a long time. But there's also this sort of underground movement of farmers and other parties that actually are trying to organise, organise themselves without the formal steps. Because they see the need of taking, you know, being faster than because we all know that policy and law is so slow in comparison to the societal changes that are needed. So I also see kind of an informal wave of change that is pushing for also for formal change more and more a lot in, yeah, in the food system and for the farmers and other organisations and. And I think Decade of Action is one of those. I think that we also push for that more because it's taking too long.

I [00:31:31] So I add informal initiatives kind of right?

P7 [00:31:39] Yeah.

I [00:31:39] So yeah. They are pushing. And do you think they also have an influence on the government in the end so.

P7 [00:31:50] Yeah. I think so. Um, I think that in a way, what we have seen so far with big revolutions and big changes in society that they usually came from bottom up. Mhm. Although there was a big change further in law as well. But the civil society movement in the in the seventies and eighties that has been coming from bottom-up for change and that actually laws were put into place because they saw the injustice of it. Mhm. So I think that again with the agricultural revolution that is coming up that you really see that the power of other that are organising themselves without the help and support of the, of the government that they're actually needed, that they are showing like okay then will do take and take and take it into our own hands and do it ourselves. I think it can have a lot of influence, um, on the formal build of society as well. Mhm. So yes, it has a lot of influence I think.

I [00:33:04] Okay. Nice. Um so we already kind of jump to the intervention, I have a feeling. So what do you think? I mean, I hear like as for the conditions, there are already interventions from last year, but I have a feeling these are more interventions towards specific regulations. Maybe first, what do you think, what are interventions to create this trust? So to, um, to get to this level of governmental support and to create this trust between government and farmers, um, can you think of any interventions there?

P7 [00:33:51] Yeah, it's a good one, I think. Of course. Yeah, it's a maybe simple word, but dialogue in that intervention is, dialogue is highly important, and I see it happening, but still not enough. I think on a regular basis and um, I think also, um, getting to get our policymakers and farmers and um, on a level that the farmers are also rewarded for giving their insights or information. So not that it's only

that they have to give, you know, because I see a lot of, um, imbalance in these kind of conversations that policymakers only visit the farms and take a lot of time of farmers, but they're not getting anything back. So enabled to make farmers being taken seriously, they need to be rewarded for actually those interactions. And those interactions are needed because the policymakers are so far from the reality that they need to be at the farm level and understand what is going on and what is needed from the farmers themselves. And those are the two big ones I think. Maybe more will come up, but those are like two big ones.

I [00:35:36] And for, because you also said that farmers, maybe it's also connected to what you just described, but farmers need for more information about regenerative agriculture. There need to be a clear definition. Would this also be covered by this dialogue or how would you. Yeah, how would you?

P7 [00:35:59] No, that's more. I think I think what would be amazing if there would be an, um, because one of the things that is not there at the moment is information exchange, exchange with the farmers.

I [00:36:13] Mm hmm.

P7 [00:36:14] On a bigger level. On a more structural level. I think there's a lot of corporations and a lot of, um. There's a lot of contact with, between farmers, but would be amazing if there is, like, this online or a platform or something where they can really interact with each other on a daily basis. And exchanging their experiences because, um, and then on that sort of context-based way. So maybe, uh, with the different soil types those farmers are or the different or when, when they are like have cattle or something. They need to be of course different typologies of farmers. But I think that will be very interesting if that can be better structured, like this sort of exchange, you know, experience based.

I [00:37:09] And just a general question, what on what level would this be? Do you have any feeling for that? So is it like local or regional, national, or is this, um.

P7 [00:37:19] I think that would be national and regional, I think. And I think European would be amazing, but I think it's still difficult to organise that, but if it was per country on a national basis, but also on the regional at the same time, I think that would be really interesting. Yeah.

I [00:37:41] Mm hmm. Okay. Nice. And for those, that are more like to go more into the specific regulations, um, what kind of regulations would be helpful. So if we say, okay, we have this trust, the

government is super supportive, what do you think, what would be, what are interventions that are really helpful for farmers to transition to regenerative agriculture?

P7 [00:38:16] Of course money.

I [00:38:18] Okay. Okay. So finance.

P7 [00:38:21] Because there's a lot of things that they need to do now, but they're not being paid for it. I think that's what. I think a lot of farmers say like, if there will be financial space for this. I mean, I mean that then I would do it. But now it's just I don't, I don't get, um, the, the rewards for biodiversity. Um. And changes in my land. Um, I think that would be the main thing. But I think what's really important is that regulation and policy is not. Yeah, that it's more measured on the outcome of it.

[00:39:03] Mm hmm.

[00:39:05] That you really can see how where farmers are going. Um, and, um. And also, what I found is that it's important to reward farmers that are already there for a long time, also, because I think there's a lot of farmers that. What you have see now actually also in the Netherlands that they have policy that they, they are being rewarded KPIs [Key-Performance Indicators?] of the farm, the business on a level that they see the change, but they're not looking at what they were beginning with because there are a lot of farmers who are working really, really hardly on making these changes without the support already. And they're being rewarded less because they're already working from a they already have like a pretty good decent farm. So they get less rewarded. But firms who are doing really badly before have higher impact because they're level they are starting from is worse than farms that are, you know. So I think there's a big gap in that sense. How can you already take along farmers that are already in that transition for many years? Um, I think that, that's also a really important one. Um. So it also is very, how to say, for example, if your if your neighbour farmer, who is a very who is a very intensive farm, use a lot of pesticides, have very poor soil and then starts to make steps, but you are already ahead of him, Your reduction of pesticide is 50% and your soil is already better. I mean, it's very sort of, um, um, I say. Um, not very motivating that he gets awards for his changes, while you've been doing it for many years. And you're not getting that at the same level. So I think it's those things that are not being seen. And, you know, and it's also very social and, and about the same trust.

I [00:41:22] So it's also a question of fairness I think. I mean, people already took the effort to implement, like, practices or regenerative practices, have, like no, don't get rewarded at all.

P7 [00:41:37] Yeah.

I [00:41:39] Okay. And do you think there are also interventions on the. So we talked a lot about the farmers side. Are there also interventions from the government with regard to the consumer side? So with regard to the people, the public.

P7 [00:41:56] Yeah. I mean, um, I think true pricing was already there, but I think it's important to of course it's, it's so strange that we pay more money for food that is bad for us and bad for environment or less than for food that is really good for the environment and good for us. It needs to be the other way around. Um, and also I think, um, it would be amazing if not only from NGOs but also from the government that they're actually giving best practices like showing to consumers and to other people. Like this is what the healthy food looks like and we're supporting these farmers to transition because this is what a healthy food, but also healthy, yeah, food cycle could look like. And would be amazing if that also comes not only from NGOs and organisation that are working in this field, but also from the government. That would also help. Yeah. On a more informal level, it's more on a, but it's also about I think if you look at interventions, there's there's a lot of interventions going on on the more lower level of a transition. You know, paradigm shifts are about our values and what we think is important. And if you start to organise more on that and also from the government perspective, if you show like this is how we want to live, this is our vision of what our food and our lives could look like. That is more on the paradigm shift based and on just numbers. And um, so that could be, it's very interesting to look more on that level of policy, um, because then you're actually pressuring, you are pushing the buttons of real societal change, then just, um, yeah, lower level societal change that is more, um, yeah.

I [00:43:58] Yeah, yeah. I mean, it has also something to do with, I mean, the government, I think they're quite afraid of their electors, so of people, that they lose the election. So they, um, kind of the don't do anything which is maybe against the majority of the population in the first place. Um, but yeah, that's might be.

P7 [00:44:21] That's really difficult. But, but I think if, if, if all sort of, you know, politics but on the other level is if it would be much more on how do we want to live together, instead of what laws are, need to be there or what kind of regulations need to be there for it not to have bad impact.

I [00:44:41] Mm hmm.

P7 [00:44:41] I mean, it's a start, but it's not. If you look at regenerative as a definition, it's much it's much broader and much more, um, um, again, like on very essential ways of living and not so much about, okay, if we put this in place that this doesn't happening, I mean, I think if, if we would communicate that more also from, from a governmental perspective, people can choose, um, yeah,

um, politicians from how they look, what their vision is more. Mm hmm. How, how much their, how much you have to pay for taxes if you choose them. I think it would be. I mean, this is of course, dreaming big. I know this is so far from what we are at the moment, but I think that is something where we should move towards. But yeah. It's difficult of course.

I [00:45:35] Yeah. I see. Um, yeah, maybe another question for me is so which was mentioned a lot was is the question of lobbying, um, and so there are these four post-its around, okay, lobbying against regenerative agriculture, dominance of conventional agriculture institutions, lobbying for regenerative agriculture, putting pressure on companies to offer regenerative products. And what do you think about that? So what? Yeah, what is your opinion on the role of lobbying in the law and policy.

P7 [00:46:14] From and from different parties?

I [00:46:19] So yeah, I mean, I think in the other interviews it was a lot about the agricultural lobby, so about big food corporations, about the big agricultural companies who support conventional agriculture because there aren't a lot of money and that this lobby has also a big influence on the government, on the current government, especially in the Netherlands. That's what I learned from from the other interviews. Um, and the question of, okay, is there a possibility of a counter lobby, how to create a counter lobby, something like this? Um, yeah.

P7 [00:46:59] Yeah. Um. I find this very difficult because they have so much influence because the amount of money they have and how they can distribute themselves everywhere over the world. Um, I mean, it's hard to fight that in the same level because you have to fight on the same, you know, um, and I think, um, I find really difficult actually because I don't know if fighting against it is so helpful. I think it's better to organise yourselves among yourselves with what you want to achieve. Um, on that sense, better than fighting against what they're doing.

I [00:47:49] Okay.

P7 [00:47:50] If you know what I mean?

I [00:47:51] Yeah.

P7 [00:47:52] Um, because I. I've been working also with pesticides on this level a lot. And it's so, it's so hard to get through this and it's so completely. I don't know. It's yeah, I would like a year ago, I would say so much more, but now I feel like again, you have to organise yourselves better and know what you want and know what you and how you get there. But I don't know, fighting the old is

sometimes, it's so hard and it takes up so much energy and so much time and so much money. I'm in this, I'm in this sort of email, uh, with, um, and I do think that lobbying is important, but I think on the level off the, the, the, the parties that you're mentioning, if you ever be able to do it on that level, I'm not sure. I think pointing out how, what the benefits are of the other system is more effective sometimes than fighting the old. Um, so I would say now. And this is in this interview because I have a lot of different opinions on it and I've been reading a lot about it, but for now I feel this is like the most effective one.

I [00:49:14] Okay. Mhm. Yeah. It's, it's super interesting. I mean you're not the only one. I had one person in another interview who also said it doesn't make sense to change. So to, to fight the system, to fight the current system, it makes more change to put effort in new initiatives and new projects and to kind of try to make another direction instead of fighting the old.

P7 [00:49:36] Yeah and I do think lobbying is part of what I do, and it's part of my other work as well. And I, I, I, I still think having these conversations about, um, and showing how effective it is on many levels, I mean, if you look at, if you read the articles around regenerative agriculture and the, the benefits of that, I mean, you cannot go around it. I mean it's so, it's so convincing. So if you can get that message across, I mean within lobbying I think that is, that is the part of lobbying that is, I think that is needed. But I think it's also more on a personal level sometimes like the lobbying I did so far with the approach I did on a personal level, I got sometimes got more, you know, get through to people and these stories and others are thinking lobbying better of organised organising and protesting and showing and, uh, being with a lot of fire. So I think that's, that dynamic is, is important that you have the people organising themselves on that, on that level like really fighting. Mhm. But also like my way of and the way I see Decade of Action also working and other projects is through showing that, yeah, how we, how our, our world would look like if we have regenerative agriculture. Mhm. Um, I think that's a strong, strong message. Yeah.

I [00:51:15] Showing. So showing the benefits of regenerative agriculture. I mean, this would also help, like everything that we just like that we said before, right, to, like, promote the vision and something like this. Yeah.

P7 [00:51:40] Yeah. Yeah.

I [00:51:43] Nice. Okay. So, um, yeah, maybe. I mean, we already started. I mean, I added this as a consequence, but can you think of other things that would. I mean, it's a similar question but would result from like a perfect governmental support. So what are kind of, um, yeah, what, what is, what is the outcome? What could be a nice outcome from that. I mean, we have like then good regulations.

P7 [00:52:15] A happy place.

I [00:52:16] What? A happy place? Um, I mean, I think trust is already also a nice outcome, actually.

P7 [00:52:28] Yeah. I mean, it feels more like a collaboration than the policy from, um, from putting policy in place that from a, how I say, like a more authoritative way. I think that collaboration way of thinking um because of the understanding of the context and of the information that is needed, the definition of regenerative agriculture and um, and how farmers are really working really hard to get there, um, without actually to support that is needed, which is crazy. I think if, if people, if policymakers and if the government would support in that way that is needed, that it would be more of a collaboration. I think in that sense. So that would be one of the consequences. Mhm. Yeah.

I [00:53:32] Mm hmm. No, I mean it's fine. And I have one more or two more questions. And one is. So we already discussed a few barriers in a way. So you mentioned the distrust. Um, and, I mean, we quickly discussed the lobbying and the dominance of conventional agriculture institutions. Are there any more barriers that, like, hinder or that more hinder that the government is more supportive at the moment or what? Yeah. What? Why is it not happening?

P7 [00:54:11] Mm hmm. Yeah. Again, like, I don't know, if I already mentioned it, but I think it needs to be on the list, like not not having a vision. I mean, the governments are really pushing for laws that are very much from day to day and not about the whole the whole change that is needed for food, for a healthy food system. So I think that is one of the big barriers. Um. And I think we talked about trust, but again, the big barrier is that, um, is that there's a big gap between being in your office doing what you do and in reality, well, what in societies is happening, so I don't think there is like, there's enough interaction between those two, and there never has been I think in that sense. Um. Yeah. And of course. But I don't know if that's a direct barrier, but the, the in general, the, um. Yeah, the people, the politicians that are being chosen have a big influence on what kind of policy is being made and being held back. And I think that's always in general, but I really see that with every culture that's.

I [00:56:11] Mhm. Yeah. I know what you mean. Yeah. I mean that's the. Yeah, there are different parties and they have different preferences and they act differently.

P7 [00:56:28] Yeah, of course. But it's always the case with a lot of political things. But this is really a highly, highly tense political topic, I guess in a lot of countries.

I [00:56:39] Yeah.

P7 [00:56:41] Um. Oh. Yeah.

I [00:56:48] No, no, it's super good already. I mean, uh, I think, um, it would be also sufficient. And then maybe last question. I mean, I probably already know the answer, but what would you say is the most important aspect in just what you just said, the whole interview. And so what is really the key?

P7 [00:57:13] Um. Yeah. Yeah. Like I said before, the social interaction, and the trust. And building from there. And understanding. Um. That, that policy is not just policy, it's the consequences of policy are actually affecting real people. And, um, and I think this is nothing new. This is something that has been there for many, many decades. But I think now we're at a time that we're seeing that, that the policies need to be, um, connected to the real world. Um. Otherwise, we're not going anywhere. We're not getting anywhere.

I [00:58:08] I will add a sentence like that. Policy needs to be connected to the real world.

P7 [00:58:15] And real people.

I [00:58:33] Nice. Okay. I think. Yes. So, do you have anything to add that I didn't ask what you think is important, or do you have the feeling that you said everything?

P7 [00:58:46] No. And, you know, sometimes you have, like, this, this, these days, and you talk a hundred, you have, like, a lot to say. But today, yeah I mean, I can add a lot of things and there's probably much more, but, um, I'm, um, yeah, it's, I think, the most important things I said. Yeah.

I [00:59:11] Nice. Yeah. So what I would do, I will clean this up and try to create a complete like a, a diagram of it. And if it would be okay for you, I would send it again to you and ask you for feedback, just to make sure that I captured everything in the correct way and things like this.

P7 [00:59:32] Yeah.

I [00:59:33] Yeah. I mean then from I said we're we're done. So a little bit earlier so that you have a bit more time to.

P7 [00:59:43] Oh that's nice. Yeah.

I [00:59:46] Um. Yeah. Do you have anything else. Any questions, any concerns?

P7 [00:59:52] Um, no, but I'm curious about what the timeline is. So you're doing the interviews and then you're gonna write for a bit. So when are you planning to be done?

I [01:00:05] Um, so, I mean, that's like my last interview now, and I already started transcribing and analysing the interviews. So, um, I hope to be done with the research part end of June, beginning of July, and I hope I will be done with writing end of September. But. Yeah, that's my, my goal and I try to stick with that. It's kind of ambitious, but I'll see.

P7 [01:00:32] No, it's good to have a. Yeah. You can always take a step back but.

I [01:00:37] Yeah.

P7 [01:00:37] It's nice to have some pressure I guess.

I [01:00:39] Yeah.

P7 [01:00:40] My thesis also took too long and then Yeah, that's also not good.

I [01:00:45] I think it was also good to have a deadline now because now I'm like, really working on it and. Yeah, yeah.

P7 [01:00:51] Yeah, yeah. Nice. I'm curious about the outcome.

I [01:00:55] Yeah. I'll let you know. Definitely.

P7 [01:00:58] Yeah, nice. All right, let me know when you're done with it. Also about this?

I [01:01:06] So perfect. Yeah. Thank you very much again.

P7 [01:01:09] And, um. Yeah, thank. You.

I [01:01:12] And have a nice day.

P7 [01:01:14] Thank you. And I will send you the autograph.

I [01:01:16] That would be perfect. Yeah, that would be great.

P7 [01:01:19] Nice. All right. Bye.

